

Short name	Long-term storage liability	Long name	Economic implications of ambiguities in long-term storage liability
Geographical scope	All regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The CO₂ Storage Directive requires that sometime after closure (to be determined by the competent authority, but at least 20 years) the responsibility for a CO₂ storage site can be transferred from the operator to the competent authority.</p> <p>Differences in MS operationalization of the storage directive causes economic uncertainty esp. regarding cases of bankruptcies before transferral to national authorities.</p> <p>Storage operators are required to provide financial security (or an equivalent, as determined by the competent authority) to ensure that all obligations under the directive can be met, including taking corrective measures to address and leakages and paying and surrendering EU ETS emissions trading allowances for any escaped CO₂. This has economic implications and any ambiguities (e.g. in permitting processes) can cause problems for the economic viability.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	Are governments prepared to take on the long-term liability for storage once stores have closed? Does it make a difference whether the CO ₂ in them is from domestic or international sources?		
Other issues this affects	Business models, GHG accounting, liability in hubs, liability (in the legal sense)		